

OG`ZAKI TILNING PAYDO BO`LISHI HAQIDAGI BIR
NECHTA NAZARIYALAR: NUTQ KOEVOLYUTSIYASI, REM
VA ROMUL NAZARIYASI VA IMO-ISHORALAR NAZARIYASI

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ABSTRACT

Bugungi kunda asosiy aloqa vositasi hisoblangan til bundan bir necha ming yillar oldin ancha sodda shaklda paydo bo`lgan edi. Ushbu maqolada til paydo bo`lishi borasidagi nazariyalar tahlili bayon qilinadi va ularning tarixi batafsil tanishtiriladi.

Nutq koevoluytsiyasi nazariyasi dastlab ijtimoiy antropolog Roy Rappaport¹ tomonidan Kris Nayt,² Jerom Lyuis,³ Nik Enfield,⁴ Kamilla Pauer⁵ va Ian Uotts⁶ kabi antropologlar tomonidan ishlab

chiqilishidan oldin taklif qilingan. Kognitiv olim va robototexnika muhandisi Lyuk Stils⁷ ham, biologik antropolog va nevrolog Terrens Dikon kabi ushbu umumiy yondashuvning yana bir taniqli tarafdoridir.⁸

Bu olimlar "tilning kelib chiqishi nazariyasi" degan narsa bo`lishi mumkin emasligini ta'kidlaydilar. Buning sababi shundaki, til alohida moslashuv emas, balki ancha kengroq ijtimoiy jarayonning ichki jihati, ya'ni butun insoniyatning ramziy madaniyatidir⁹. Tilni kengroq kontekstdan mustaqil ravishda tushuntirishga urinishlar muvaffaqiyatsizlikka uchradi, deydi bu olimlar, chunki ular yechimi bo`lmagan

¹ Rappaport, Roy (1999). *Ritual and religion in the making of humanity*. Cambridge, U.K. New York: Cambridge University Press.

² Knight, Chris (1998). James R Hurford; Michael Studdert-Kennedy; Chris Knight (eds.). *Ritual/speech coevolution: a solution to the problem of deception*. Approaches to the evolution of language : social and cognitive base. Cambridge, UK; New York: Cambridge University Press. pp. 68–91.

³ Lewis, Jerome (2009). Rudolf P Botha; Chris Knight (eds.). *As Well as Words: Congo Pygmy Hunting, Mimicry, and Play. The cradle of language*. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press. pp. 236–256.

⁴ Enfield, N. J. (2010). "Without social context?". *Science*. 329 (5999): 1600–1601.

⁵ Power, Camilla (1998). James R Hurford; Michael Studdert-Kennedy; Chris Knight (eds.). *Old wives' tales: the gossip hypothesis and the reliability of cheap signals*. Approaches to the evolution of language : social and cognitive base. Cambridge, UK; New York: Cambridge University Press. pp. 111–129.

⁶ Watts, Ian (2009). Rudolf P Botha; Chris Knight (eds.). *Red Ochre, Body Painting, and Language: Interpreting the Blombos Ochre. The cradle of language*. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press. pp. 62–92.

⁷ Steels, L. (2009). Rudolf P. Botha; Chris Knight (eds.). *Is sociality a crucial prerequisite for the emergence of language?. The prehistory of language*. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press.

⁸ Deacon, Terrence William (1997). *The symbolic species: the co-evolution of language and the brain*. New York: W.W. Norton.

⁹ Knight, Chris (2010). Ulrich J Frey; Charlotte Störmer; Kai P Willführ (eds.). *The origins of symbolic culture* (PDF). *Homo novus : a human without illusion*. Berlin; New York: Springer. pp. 193–211.

muammoni hal qilmoqdalar. Til muayyan ijtimoiy mexanizmlar va institutlar majmuasidan tashqarida ishlamaydi. Masalan, yovvoyi tabiatda odam bo'lmagan maymunlarning boshqalar bilan muloqot qilishiga buning aloqasi yo`q. Chunki bunday sharoitda hatto eng aqlli maymun ham tilni ishlata olmaydi.

Ushbu tafakkur maktabi tarafdorlari so'zlarning arzon (qadrsiz) ekanligini ta'kidlashadi. Ayniqsa aqlli odam bo'lmagan maymun yoki hatto odam bo'lmagan artikulyativ maymunlar guruhi yovvoyi tabiatda so'zlarni ishlatishga harakat qilgan taqdirda ham, ular soxta hisoblanadi. Ishonchli bo'lgan primat tovushlari esa - ular haqiqatda ishlatadiganlari - so'zlardan farqli ravishda, hissiy jihatdan ifodali, mazmunli va ishonchlidir. Chunki ularni soxtalashtirish qiyin.

Til narxi asosan nolga teng bo'lgan kontrastlardan iborat. Sof ijtimoiy konventsional sifatida bunday signallar darvinchi ijtimoiy dunyoda rivojlana olmaydi - ular nazariy jihatdan imkonsizdir.¹⁰ Til o'z mohiyatiga ko'ra ishonchsiz bo'lib, faqat ma'lum bir jamiyatda ishonchlilik obro'siga ega bo'lsa, ya'ni ramziy madaniy faktlar (ba'zan "institutsional faktlar" deb ataladi) jamoaviy ijtimoiy ma'qullash orqali o'rnatilishi va saqlanishi mumkin bo'lgan taqdiridagina ishlaydi.¹¹ Har qanday ovchiyig'uvchi jamiyatda ramziy madaniy faktlarga ishonchni o'rnatishning asosiy mexanizmi jamoaviy marosimdir.¹² Shu

sababli, tilning kelib chiqishi tadqiqotchilari oldida turgan vazifa odatdagidan ko'ra ko'p tarmoqli. Bu til muhim, ammo yordamchi komponent sifatida butun insoniyat ramziy madaniyatining evolutsion paydo bo'lishini ko'rib chiqishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Rem va Romul nazariyasi

Neyrobiolog Andrey Vyshedskiy tomonidan taklif qilingan Romul va Rem gipotezasi zamonaviy nutq apparati nima uchun zamonaviy inson tasavvurining dastlabki belgilaridan 500 000 yil oldin paydo bo'lganligi haqidagi savolga javob berishga intiladi. Ushbu gipoteza zamonaviy rekursiv tilga olib keladigan ikki bosqich mavjudligini taklif qiladi. Rekursiya hodisasi bir nechta lingvistik sohalarda, ehtimol sintaksis va morfologiyada eng ko'p uchraydi. Shunday qilib, jumla yoki so'z kabi tuzilmani o'z ichiga joylashtirish orqali bu strukturaning potentsial cheksiz yangi o'zgarishlarini yaratishga imkon beradi. Misol uchun, «Piter olmani yoqtiradi» tayanch jumlasiga bir nechta irrealis bo'laklarni qo'shish mumkin: *Maryam aytdi: «Piter olmani yaxshi ko'radi», «Paul Maryam Piter olmani yaxshi ko'rishini aytganiga ishondi»* va hokazo.¹³

Birinchi bosqich zamonaviy nutq apparati bilan bir qatorda katta lug'atga ega bo'lgan rekursiv bo'lmagan tilning sekin rivojlanishini o'z ichiga oladi, bu gioid suyagidagi o'zgarishlar, diafragma mushaklarining ixtiyoriy nazoratini kuchaytirish, FOXP2 genining

¹⁰ Zahavi, A. (May 1993). "The fallacy of conventional signalling". *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. 340 (1292): 227–230.

¹¹ Searle, J. R. 1996. *The Construction of Social Reality*. London: Penguin.

¹² Durkheim, E. 1947 [1915]. "Origins of these beliefs". Chapter VII. In E. Durkheim, *The Elementary Forms of the*

Religious Life: A study in religious sociology. Trans. J. W. Swain. Glencoe, Illinois: The Free Press, pp. 205–239.

¹³ [Carnie, Andrew](#) (2012). [Syntax: A Generative Introduction](#) (3rd ed.). West Sussex, UK: Wiley-Blackwell. pp. 20–21.

evolyutsiyasi, shuningdek. 600 000 yil oldin sodir bo'lgan boshqa o'zgarishlarni o'z ichiga oladi.¹⁴

Keyin, ikkinchi bosqich, taxminan 70 000 yil oldin ketma-ket sodir bo'lgan uchta aniq hodisadan iborat bo'lgan Xomskiyning bir nazariyasini, erta gominlarda rekursiv bo'lmagan tildan rekursiv tilga o'tishga imkon berishini asoslab beradi.

1. Birgalikda yashagan kamida ikkita bolaning prefrontal sintezining (PFS) kritik davrini sekinlashtirgan genetik mutatsiya.

2. Bu bolalarga xayoliy predloglar kabi tilning rekursiv elementlarini yaratishga imkon berdi.

3. Keyin bu ularning ota-onalarining rekursiv bo'lmagan tili bilan birlashib, yangi rekursiv tilni yaratdi.¹⁵

Bolalar uchun PFS rivojlanishiga imkon berish uchun zamonaviy prefrontal korteksning (PFC) bo'lishi yetarli emas; PFSni o'zlashtirish uchun bolalar aqlan rag'batlantirilishi va ularning tili allaqachon rekursiv elementlarga ega bo'lishi kerak. Ularning ota-onalari hali bu elementlarni ixtiro qilmaganliklari sababli, bolalar buni o'zlari qilishlari talab etiladi, bu *kriptofaziya* deb ataladigan jarayonda birga yashaydigan yosh bolalar orasida keng tarqalgan hodisadir.¹⁶ Bu shuni anglatadiki, PFC rivojlanishining

¹⁴ Dediu, Dan; Levinson, Stephen C. (2013). "[On the antiquity of language: the reinterpretation of Neandertal linguistic capacities and its consequences](#)". *Frontiers in Psychology*. 4: 397.

¹⁵ Vyshedskiy, Andrey (29 July 2019). "[Language evolution to revolution: the leap from rich-vocabulary non-recursive communication system to recursive language 70,000 years ago was associated with acquisition of a novel component of imagination, called Prefrontal Synthesis, enabled by a mutation that slowed down the prefrontal cortex maturation simultaneously in two or more children – the Romulus and Remus hypothesis](#)". Research Ideas and Outcomes.

¹⁶ Bakker, Peter (July 1987). "Autonomous Languages of Twins". *Acta Geneticae Medicae et Gemellologiae: Twin Research*. 36 (2): 233–238.

kechiktirilishi PFSni olish va rekursiv elementlarni ishlab chiqish uchun ko'proq vaqt ajratgan bo'lar edi.

Imo-ishoralar nazariyasi

Imo-ishoralar nazariyasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, inson tili oddiy muloqot uchun ishlatiladigan imo-ishoralardan rivojlangan. Ikki turdagi dalillar bu nazariyani qo'llab-quvvatlaydi:

- Imo-ishora tili va ovozli til o'xshash nerv sistemalariga bog'liq. Og'iz va qo'l harakati uchun mas'ul bo'lgan korteksdagi hududlar bir-biri bilan chegaradosh.

- Odam bo'lmagan primatlar hech bo'lmaganda ibtidoiy muloqot uchun imo-ishoralar yoki belgilardan foydalanishi mumkin va ularning ba'zi imo-ishoralari odamlarnikiga o'xshaydi, masalan, odamlar shimpanzalar bilan qo'llari cho'zilgan "yolvoruvchi holat"ni bo'lishadi.¹⁷

Tadqiqotlar og'zaki til va imo-ishora tili o'xshash nerv tuzilmalariga bog'liq degan fikrni kuchli qo'llab-quvvatladi. Imo-ishora tilini ishlatgan va chap yarim sharning shikastlanishidan aziyat chekkan bemorlar, ovozli bemorlar og'zaki nutqida bo'lgani kabi, imo-ishora tilida ham bir xil kasalliklarni boshdan kechiradi.¹⁸ Boshqa tadqiqotchilar imo-ishora tili paytida ham xuddi shunday chap yarim sharning miya hududlari ovozli yoki yozma tildan foydalanish paytida faol ekanligini aniqladilar.

¹⁷ Pollick, AS.; de Waal, FB. (May 2007). "[Ape Gestures and Language Evolution](#)". Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America. 104 (19)

¹⁸ Kimura, Doreen (1993). *Neuromotor mechanisms in human communication*. New York: Oxford University Press.

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3. Ziyodillaeva Mahbuba Ermatovna. (2022). ITERLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF AMERICAN ENGLISH AND MEXICAN SPANISH. SOCIOLINGUISTIC RESEARCH ON CHICANO ENGLISH. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(2), 328–332.
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